

nextGEMS

Next Generation Earth Modelling Systems

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About this document

Based on the evaluation of high-resolution ocean models in comparison with observations of tropical ocean mixing processes, recommendations will be given for improved formulations in mixed-layer models to be used in the application phase.

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WP6

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1 Executive summary

This reports describes the sensitivity studies undertaken with the two NextGEMS ocean models ICON-O and FESOM (for IFS) and two mixed layer parameterizations. Both groups decided to move forward with the Turbulent Kinetic Energy (TKE) scheme with parameter settings that are different from the original formulation (for ICON-O: $c_k = 0.1$ instead of $c_k = 0.2$).

2 Conclusion & Results

We investigated two different mixed layer schemes, each one of which is implemented in both models, and modified various parameters in these schemes. We find that both schemes, in all parameter combinations underestimate the mixed layer depth in the tropical Atlantic. However, the differences between the two ML models is smaller than the difference created by using different bulk flux formulae, so it was decided to use the TKE scheme, because it is deemed to be more easy to connect to other model physics than the competing K-Profile Parameterization (KPP) scheme. In particular the parameterization for abyssal turbulence (IDEMIX), which will be included in the models in the near future, is TKE based.

3 Project objectives

The following table lists the overall objectives of nextGEMS. Objectives that the current report contributes to are flagged with yes.

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
O1	
To develop two SR-ESMs for applications	
(i) by demonstrating their capacity to more realistically represent the coupled (land-ocean-atmosphere) climate system, also through an ability to better leverage observations;	yes
(ii) by performing the first global multi-decadal (30 y) SR-ESM based climate projections, testing for out-of-sample climate trajectories, i.e., surprises, and thereby giving a new perspective on uncertainty; and	yes
(iii) by expanding their scope to begin more physically coupling 'Earth-system' processes, including the carbon cycle and the atmospheric aerosol	yes
O2	

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
To use SR-ESMs to test emerging and long-standing hypotheses underpinning our understanding of climate change:	
(i) that convective organization contributes importantly to Earth's energy budget and the strength of cloud feedbacks;	no
(ii) that a more explicit representation of cloud-aerosol interactions mutes aerosol-radiative forcing;	no
(iii) that 2 km to 200 km scale atmospheric and oceanic circulations are of leading order importance for air-sea fluxes in the tropics, thereby influencing not only the mean tropical and mid-latitude climate, but also its variability, including extremes;	yes
(iv) that storm-scale variability in weather systems and of the land surface strongly influence extra-tropical climate and extremes, for instance by conditioning circulation regimes, like blocking;	no
(v) that capturing landscape variability globally greatly improves the realism with which regional climate can be simulated; and	no
(vi) that storm-scale variability through its impact on hydrological extremes affects the carbon budget, with associated implications for the global carbon (emissions) stock-take.	no
O3	
To build new, more integrated, communities of ESM users by:	
(i) exploiting the necessity of developing SR-ESMs around a centralized infrastructure to create development and analysis paradigms that can more directly involve a broader and more distributed scientific community; and	no
(ii) by exploiting the affinity between what people experience and what SR-ESMs simulate (i.e., events, in addition to statistics) to more directly involve non-scientific users in model development, thereby fostering Knowledge Coproduction.	no

This deliverable directly contributes to the achievement of specific objectives indicated in the description of the Work Package:

Objectives of WP6	Relevance in this deliverable?
To identify and evaluate key ocean and marine atmosphere features in the SR-ESM simulations of all three development cycles. (O1)	yes
To validate the marine planetary boundary layer representation of the SR-ESM simulations. (O1)	yes
To provide ocean initial conditions for the coupled SR-ESM simulations. (O1)	yes
To provide developments towards an ocean mixed layer scheme adequate for SR-ESMs. (O1)	yes
To create numerical tools that generate output streams useful to the planetary boundary layer, ocean mixed-layer and fisheries communities. (O1,O3)	yes

4 Detailed report on the deliverable

Note: Most of the analysis below is based on an analysis that is led by Swantje Bastin, and who is currently preparing a publication, which will be submitted this fall.

To run the coordinated sensitivity experiments, we agreed on a common vertical axis with 128 vertical levels, varying from 2 m level thickness close to the surface to approximately 200 m thickness close to the bottom. The original level thickness of 10m proved to lead to a too shallow mixed layer (see detailed analysis below and Figure 1), so that both groups decided to use this high resolution version.

Figure 1: Difference in annual mean mixed layer depth in FESOM for three different model resolution. Comparison of the middle and right panel shows that vertical resolution is much more important than horizontal resolution for the tropical mixed layer depth.

We agreed that the only differences between the two model versions should be the representation of the ocean grid. We tested two different representations of the ocean mixed layer:

1) the empirical K-Profile Parameterization (KPP, Large et al. 1994), in which the mixed layer depth is determined based on a Richardson number criterium and the diffusivity within that mixed layer is based on an empirically determined quadratic function.

2) the Turbulent Kinetic Energy based TKE scheme (Gaspar et al., 1990), in which for every model layer the equation for TKE is solved under certain closure assumptions, and the mixed layer then evolves if the TKE budget indicates a change in the mixed layer depth.

In the TKE scheme, we vary the c_k parameter (see below). For the KPP scheme, we run the models once with the default setting of $Ri_{crit} = 0.3$, and once with a reduced value of $Ri_{crit} = 0.27$. We do this because of the resolution dependence of the critical bulk Richardson number: the finer the vertical resolution, the closer the critical bulk Richardson number should be to the theoretical critical value for the gradient Richardson number which is 0.25. The different model runs with their parameter settings are listed in Table 3.

Table 3: Overview of model runs used in this study

Name	Model	Hor. resolution	Mixing scheme	Parameter settings
I_40	ICON-O	40km	TKE	$c_k = 0.2$
I_10	ICON-O	10km	TKE	$c_k = 0.2$
I_5	ICON-O	5km	TKE	$c_k = 0.2$
F_TKE_01	FESOM	10km	TKE	$c_k = 0.1$
F_TKE_02	FESOM	10km	TKE	$c_k = 0.2$
F_TKE_03	FESOM	10km	TKE	$c_k = 0.3$
F_KPP_030	FESOM	10km	KPP	$Ri_{crit} = 0.3$
F_KPP_027	FESOM	10km	KPP	$Ri_{crit} = 0.27$
I_TKE_01	ICON-O	10km	TKE	$c_k = 0.1$
I_TKE_02	ICON-O	10km	TKE	$c_k = 0.2$
I_TKE_03	ICON-O	10km	TKE	$c_k = 0.3$
I_KPP_030	ICON-O	10km	KPP	$Ri_{crit} = 0.3$
I_KPP_027	ICON-O	10km	KPP	$Ri_{crit} = 0.27$
I_Langmuir	ICON-O	10km	TKE	additional Langmuir parameterisation (Axell, 2002)
I_minTKE	ICON-O	10km	TKE	minimum background TKE
I_minkv	ICON-O	10km	TKE	minimum background diffusivity

We force all model runs with hourly ERA5 data, and run them from the spinup with the adjusted mixing parameter settings for two years (2014 and 2015). Of these, we analyse only the second year when the mixed layer has adjusted to the changed mixing settings. The year 2015 was chosen because a particularly strong Near-Inertial Wave (NIW) mixing event occurred in that year and was observed during a RV Meteor cruise in the tropical North Atlantic, as described and analysed by Hummels et al. (2020). We want to compare this unique set of observations against our models to assess whether they can reproduce deep reaching NIW mixing events like the one observed in 2015.

Although we tried to homogenise the model settings that are directly connected to the representation of vertical mixing, it emerged during an early ocean-only hackathon that several details are different between the model configurations. This, of course, is part of the reason why these comparisons are so important, to see how much of the variation between the different verti-

cal mixing settings is model specific and how much happens similarly in both models. Some of the differences between ICON-O and FESOM include a different default set of bulk formulae to convert the atmospheric forcing fields from ERA5 to air-sea fluxes (the former accounts for ocean surface velocity in the bulk formulae, the latter does not). Because the forcing bulk formulae seem to have quite a large influence on some of the variables we look at, we did an additional run with ICON-O using the FESOM bulk formulae to clarify how much of the inter-model differences are due to this.

4.1 Mean tropical mixed layer depth

An important metric to check the performance of the vertical mixing parameterisation is the depth of the surface ocean mixed layer. In Figure 2, the 2015 annual mean Mixed Layer Depth (MLD) in the tropical Atlantic is shown for ICON-O and FESOM together with a climatology derived from Argo float observations (Argo, 2022). The MLD has been calculated from the models and all available Argo float profiles in the tropical Atlantic using a density criterion (potential density exceeds the surface density by 0.03 km m^{-3}). Existing MLD climatologies normally use a density or temperature threshold compared to 10 m depth instead of the surface, and are thus unfortunately not suited for the tropical oceans where the MLD can be very shallow (Holte et al., 2017). It is visible that in both ICON-O and FESOM, the MLD is generally too shallow in the equatorial Atlantic compared to the Argo float climatology. In the TKE runs, the bias is especially large on the equator. In Figure 4, the mean MLD along the equator is shown for the different model runs together. KPP is much closer to observations than TKE for both FESOM and ICON-O. From the TKE runs, a common pattern emerges: with smaller c_k , the equatorial MLD becomes deeper, i.e. more realistic. This is counterintuitive, because a larger c_k should lead to larger viscosity and diffusivity. However, the change in c_k also leads to differences in the density and current structure, which in turn changes the amount of TKE and can thus eventually lead to reduced mixing. Here, the main factor leading to a larger equatorial MLD with smaller c_k is very likely the Equatorial Undercurrent, which is a source of shear instability, but becomes weaker with increasing c_k . We explore this in more detail in Section 4.4.

Figure 2: Annual mean mixed layer depth (MLD) in the tropical Atlantic Ocean from Argo float data (climatological mean over entire available measurement period from 2000 to 2022) and sensitivity model runs from FESOM and ICON-O (mean over second integration year 2015). The MLD has been calculated using a commonly used density threshold criterion, where the MLD is defined as the depth at which the potential density exceeds the surface density by more than 0.03 kg m^{-3} .

North of the equator, the mixed layer actually becomes deeper and thus closer to observations with increasing c_k in both FESOM and ICON-O (see Figure 3).

Figure 3: Difference in annual mean mixed layer depth between FESOM and ICON-O runs and Argo float data in the tropical Atlantic Ocean.

Figure 4: Annual mean Atlantic Ocean mixed layer depth along the equator (averaged between 4°S and 4°N) from Argo float data as well as FESOM and ICON-O.

Contrary to what one might believe, the too shallow mixed layer in the models is actually made worse by higher horizontal resolution. This corroborates results by (Lévy et al., 2010) based on idealised regional model experiments, who suggested increased restratification by submesoscale processes as an important effect of increased resolution. However, by comparing the 5km and 10km resolution results (not shown), we find that at least in the tropical Atlantic the effect of extra submesoscale activity is minor (unlike changing the resolution from 40 to 10km), so that the remaining sensitivity experiments are carried out at 10 km resolution.

4.2 Mean surface temperature distribution

Tropical Sea Surface Temperature (SST) affects atmospheric convection, and can thus influence large scale tropical and also extratropical wind and precipitation patterns. It is thus quite important to simulate the tropical SST distribution well in climate models. In Figure 5, the annual mean 2015 sea surface temperature in the tropical Atlantic is shown for HadISST on the left, and the difference to HadISST in the different model runs in the centre column (ICON-O) and right column (FESOM). In both models, a typical warm bias in the upwelling regions along the African coast can be seen that has been a long-standing bias in most ocean and climate models (e.g. Farneti et al., 2022). Compared to CMIP6 models, the eastern warm bias in ICON-O and FESOM is rather small (e.g. Richter and Tokinaga, 2020; Farneti et al., 2022), maybe owing to the high horizontal resolution used in this study – Richter and Tokinaga (2020) and Farneti et al. (2022) find that the SST biases in HighResMIP are reduced compared to standard CMIP6. However, the largest bias in ICON-O and FESOM is not the warm bias in the east, but a very strong cold bias in the central and western tropical Atlantic. This cold bias has a similar pattern in both models, with an intensification on the equator, but is significantly stronger in ICON-O than in FESOM.

Especially in FESOM, almost no effect of changing the vertical mixing scheme or the associated parameters is visible on the mean tropical Atlantic SST bias. In ICON-O, changes between some of the different runs are visible, but never enough to change the large scale pattern of the bias or reduce it significantly: in all cases the western equatorial cold bias stays larger in ICON-O than it is in FESOM. The eastern warm bias is reduced in ICON-O when using KPP. In the west, the cold bias becomes larger in the ICON-O TKE runs when using a large value of $c_k = 0.3$.

Figure 5: Annual mean 2015 Atlantic Ocean sea surface temperature from the HadISST dataset as well as FESOM and ICON-O (for the models, differences to HadISST are shown, blue colours meaning the model is colder than HadISST).

4.3 Mean vertical temperature distribution

In Figure 6, vertical sections of the annual mean 2015 temperature are shown for the upper 200 m along the equator of the tropical Atlantic. The panel on the left shows a mean temperature section from Argo float data, the centre panels show the difference to Argo for ICON-O, the right panels for FESOM. Along the equator, there is a cold bias above the thermocline and a warm bias below it in all model runs. The biases are again generally stronger in ICON-O than in FESOM, as for the mean SST. In the warm bias below the thermocline, some reactions to changes in the mixing scheme can be seen that are actually consistent between the two models: the bias becomes stronger when c_k is increased in the TKE scheme, and it is also stronger in KPP than in TKE (although this is not so obvious in FESOM). As seen before, the changes between the different FESOM runs are actually not very large, while ICON-O reacts more sensitively to changes in the vertical mixing parameterization. Including the Langmuir parameterization does not have a large effect. Increasing the background TKE has a similar effect as increasing c_k in the TKE scheme: both the cold bias above the thermocline and the warm bias below the thermocline increase (i.e. the thermocline becomes more diffuse). Increasing the minimum background diffusivity does not significantly change the biases.

4.4 Equatorial current system

The equatorial oceans are characterized by strong zonal current systems. An important part of these is the Equatorial Undercurrent (EUC), which is one of the strongest subsurface currents in the world oceans. It transports water eastward approximately at the depth of the thermocline along the equator, and contributes to the Meridional Overturning Circulation (MOC) and the Subtropical Cells (e.g. [Jochum and Malanotte-Rizzoli, 2001](#); [Johns et al., 2014](#)). The EUC is not only important for horizontal water transport, but also for vertical mixing in the equatorial ocean: due to the shear between the mean westward surface flow of the South Equatorial Current and the eastward flow of the EUC at thermocline depth, the upper equatorial water column is permanently close to a state of marginal instability. This has some interesting consequences for the generation of turbulence in the equatorial oceans, which is diurnally enhanced not only in, but also below the surface mixed layer ([Smyth et al., 2013](#); [Moum et al., 2022](#)). On the other hand, it has been shown that the EUC is notoriously hard to simulate in ocean models (e.g. [Karnauskas et al., 2020](#); [Fu et al., 2022](#)), and that it reacts relatively sensitively to e.g. the vertical mixing parameterization (e.g. [McCreary, 1981](#)). We therefore take a closer look at how the Atlantic EUC is represented in ICON-O and FESOM and how it reacts to the different vertical mixing scheme settings.

In Figure 7, cross sections of the mean zonal velocity along 23°W are shown. The first panel shows a multi-year mean from shipboard observations during 25 cruises ([Brandt et al., 2021](#)). The Equatorial Undercurrent (EUC), a very strong eastward subsurface current, can be clearly seen on the equator at approximately 70 m depth. In the cruise observations, it has a mean core velocity of 0.79 m s^{-1} . The panels in the centre column show the same for the different ICON-O runs, the panels on the right for FESOM. In general, the EUC is too weak as well as too deep and broad in ICON-O, whereas it is closer to the observed strength and location in FESOM. In both models, increasing c_k in the TKE scheme leads to a weakening and deepening of the EUC. The weakening is likely related to an increased eddy viscosity with increased c_k (not shown). Since the EUC core depth is strongly related to the depth of the thermocline, the deepening of the EUC core is likely related to changes in the stratification with increasing c_k . This is consistent with the mean temperature bias sections along the equator shown in Figure 6 where a strong

Figure 6: Vertical section along the equator of annual mean temperature from 2015, from Argo float data as well as FESOM and ICON-O.

Figure 7: Strength of the Equatorial Undercurrent (EUC) from cruise observations and FESOM and ICON-O model runs. Shown is a mean section of zonal velocity along 23°W, where multi-year cruise data are available. The observations are averaged over all available years (for details see the text), the sections from the models are annual averages over 2015.

influence of c_k on the vertical temperature gradient in the EUC depth range can be seen. In ICON-O, the EUC is most realistic with the smallest tested value of $c_k = 0.1$, although it is then still a bit too weak and too deep. Since the EUC is in general stronger and shallower in FESOM, it even becomes too strong with $c_k = 0.1$. Here, a value between 0.1 and 0.2 seems best.

Changing the vertical mixing scheme from TKE to KPP has a very different effect in ICON-O and FESOM. In ICON-O, the EUC strength reduces dramatically to below 0.3 m s^{-1} . With a lower critical bulk Richardson number of $Ri_{crit} = 0.27$, the reduction is even stronger. In FESOM, the EUC core velocity with KPP remains in the range of values for the different TKE runs, and with 0.71 m s^{-1} both for $Ri_{crit} = 0.3$ and $Ri_{crit} = 0.27$ reasonably close to the observed value of 0.79 m s^{-1} .

4.5 On the importance of proper bulk formulae.

As shown in the sections above, we generally find larger differences between the two models that we used than between different settings of the vertical mixing scheme. We were therefore interested in where the large differences between FESOM and ICON-O come from. Because of limited resources, we could test only one possible factor, and we chose the one that to us seemed to have most potential for a big impact on the mean upper ocean state: the different sets of bulk formulae in ICON-O and FESOM. Bulk formulae compute air-sea fluxes based on, among other things, the difference in speed between surface wind and surface current. Often the latter is conveniently ignored, as it is done in ICON but not in FESOM. It turns out that the differences are not trivial, at least in the tropics.

To quantify the effect of the different bulk formulae, we did an additional test run with ICON, with the same settings as in I_TKE_02, but with the bulk formulae that FESOM uses. We call this run I_TKE_02_FBF. The effect that this has on the mean tropical Atlantic SST can be seen in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Effect of exchanging the forcing bulk formulae in ICON-O on the 2015 annual mean sea surface temperature.

For the mixed layer depth and zonal current velocity, the two ICON-O runs look very similar (not shown). Here, the bulk formulae do not seem to make much difference, suggesting that other factors lead to the different mean MLD pattern in the model. These could include differences in lateral mixing, in the horizontal grid, or in the numerics.

In contrast to that, the sea surface temperature reacts strongly to the different bulk formulae (Figure 8). The SST pattern in ICON-O becomes more similar to FESOM when using the same bulk formulae, but interestingly, the entire tropical Atlantic also becomes much warmer. While ICON with its default bulk formula has a much larger cold bias in the western Atlantic than FESOM, its western cold bias reduces very much and is smaller than FESOM's when using the FESOM bulk formulae. Instead, the eastern Atlantic warm bias is then much stronger than before and than in FESOM.

The different bulk formulae that are by default applied in FESOM and ICON-O can explain a significant part of the models' differences in mean tropical Atlantic SST and EUC strength, while they do not affect the mean mixed layer depth much. However, also for SST and EUC, a large unexplained difference remains such that other factors must contribute as well.

5 Summary

Investigating the effect of different parameter settings in two vertical mixing schemes on the tropical Atlantic in ICON-O and FESOM, we find that both schemes, in all parameter combinations, underestimate the mixed layer depth in the tropical Atlantic. However, the differences between the two schemes (TKE and KPP) are generally smaller than the overall differences between the two models, and also for example smaller than the difference created by using different bulk flux formulae. It was decided to use the TKE scheme for the nextGEMS coupled runs, because it is deemed to be more easy to connect to other model physics than the competing K-Profile Parameterization (KPP) scheme. In particular the parameterization for abyssal turbulence (IDEMIX), which will be included in the models in the near future, is TKE based. For ICON-O, we furthermore decided to reduce the c_k parameter in the TKE scheme from 0.2 to 0.1. Although there are only very slight differences caused by this, our motivation for this change was that the strong equatorial surface cold bias in the western Atlantic slightly decreases with smaller c_k . In test runs with the coupled ICON model, we saw that this effect leads to a small improvement in the westerly trade wind bias that we have been struggling with in the coupled model. From the model-optimization perspective it is a bit disappointing that the MLD is so insensitive to details of its parameterization. In particular, it appears that details of the bulk formulae are much more important. On the other hand, this suggests that ML models are built on robust foundations, be they empirical (KPP) or dynamical (TKE). Furthermore, it appears that we as a group, or the field as a whole, should spend more time investigating the parameterization of air-sea fluxes.

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7 Dissemination and uptake

7.1 Uptake by the targeted audience

As indicated in the Description of the Action, the audience for this deliverable is:

x	The general public (PU)
	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This reports is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

7.2 This is how we are going to ensure the uptake of the deliverables by the targeted audience

The main deliverable here is a recommendation of which mixed layer parameterization in which configuration should be used. The recommendation was made and has already been followed by both participating SR-ESMs. Furthermore our results are currently written up for a peer reviewed publication so that other modelling groups can benefit from our experiences.

8 Deliverable timeliness

Is the deliverable delayed?

no

9 Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any

Originally we proposed to also evaluate a third mixed layer model, the $k - \epsilon$ model. It is a model that evolved from the TKE model investigated here. However, since modifications to the TKE model had only minor impact on the biases, we decided to instead use the resources to investigate the effect of different bulk formulae and the Langmuir circulation (the latter being minor as well). We also planned to analyze the effect of resolution only in FESOM, and the details of the mixing schemes in ICON. However, an initial first comparison showed that the 2 models were more different than anticipated (e.g. in the bulk flux formulae), so that we ended up doing most experiments with both models.

10 Sustainability

N/A

11 Full track of dissemination activities

- Cycle 1 Hackathon 19. – 22. October 2021 in Berlin
- "Science meets Art" - NextCalendArt 2022
- Office Hour with IBERDROLA on solar energy in January 2022
- UCM Student Hackathon, 01. – 03. April 2022 near Madrid
- Cycle 2 Hackathon 26. June – 02. July 2022 in Vienna
- Storms & Ocean summer slackathon 31. July – 06. August 2022 at the Bornö Institute for ocean and climate studies, Sweden
- "Science meets Art" - NextCalendArt 2023
- Mini-hackathon of Storms & Land at Wageningen University 04. – 06. April 2023
- Cycle 3 Hackathon 29. May – 02. June 2023 in Madrid

12 Full track of publications and IP

Publications within the project can be found on our website: <https://nextgems-h2020.eu/publications/>